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Photo Corrosion of 63/37 Brass in Aqueous Solutions Containing Chloride Ions

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THE corrosion of copper in sea water in dark and sunlight has been studied by Korovin and Ulanovskii¹ and they have reported the formation of CuCl film on the metal surface. Effect of light on the kinetics of corrosion of copper has also been reported by Ivan Sekerka and co-workers². They have reported that light energy increases the rate of corrosion but not much attention has been paid to the corrosion rate of brass in aqueous solutions of both hydrochloric acid and sodium chloride.

All experiments were carried out at $40^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. The results of corrosion kinetics were expressed in terms of weight loss in presence and absence of light (Table-1). The results are also represented graphically in Fig 1. Photo current was measured by the method described previously⁴.

Fig. 1. Graph of concentration vs. loss mg/dm²/day for 63/37 brass in aqueous solutions of hydrochloric acid and sodium chloride. A-63/37 brass in HCl in presence of light; B-63/37 brass in HCl in absence of light; A'-63/37 brass in NaCl in presence of light; B'-63/37 brass in NaCl in absence of light.

TABLE : 1 WEIGHT LOSS DATA ON CORROSION OF 63/37 BRASS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF HYDROCHLORIC ACID AND SODIUM CHLORIDE

Size of the specimen : 3x6 cms

Temperature : $40^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$

Duration : 8 hrs.

Concentration of solution (Molar)	In absence of light			In presence of light		
	Loss mg	Loss mg/dm ²	Loss mg/dm ² /day	Loss mg	Loss mg/dm ²	Loss mg/dm ² /day
	Hydrochloric Acid					
0.1	5.8	16.1	48.3	9.4	26.1	78.3
0.5			63.0	12.6	35.0	105
1.0	9.8	27.2	81.6	16.4	45.5	136
	Sodium Chloride					
0.1	1.5	4.20	12.6	2.2	6.10	18.3
0.5	2.2	6.00	18.0	3.1	8.60	25.8
1.0	3.0	8.33	25.0	4.3	12.0	36.0

In the present work an attempt has been made to study the influence of white light (sunlight) on corrosion rate of 63/37 brass when a photosensitive and semi-conducting films are formed as corrosion products on the brass specimens.

Experimental

63/37 brass specimens were used in all experiments. The specimens were cleaned and polished according to the methods suggested by Champion³. Specimens were degreased in sulphur free carbon tetrachloride. The weighed specimens were immersed in 250 ml test solutions i.e. 0.1, 0.5 and 1M aqueous HCl as well as 0.1, 0.5 and 2.0M aqueous NaCl solutions. The experiment was carried out in duplicate, One of the duplicate sets was exposed to white light while the other was shielded from it. After a duration of eight hours all the plates were removed and cleaned by 5% sulphuric acid solution. The reproducibility of the weight loss data is ± 1 mg.

Discussion

Dezincification takes place when brass is dipped in aqueous solution of hydrochloric acid as well as sodium chloride solution. Both solutions contain Cl⁻ ions which react with copper forming CuCl film. This is deposited on the plate surface which gives a reddish brown film. CuCl is photo-sensitive and a n-type semiconductor, hence produces photo current when white light falls on it. The investigation of photo conduction in single crystal has revealed that holes as well as electrons contribute to photo current at all temperatures. Excitation produced by light beam can migrate before dissociation⁵. In both the cases the colour of the film is brown and when the plate is further exposed to light the colour of the film changes from brown to greenish blue and finally bluish-black. This is in accordance with the property of CuCl. Moreover, when the film is exposed to white light a photo current of 0.38 micro ampere is obtained.

This was noted experimentally. Due to inhomogeneous excitation photo voltage produced decomposes water⁶.

Due to photo electric current and decomposition of H₂O the corrosion rate increases in presence of white light (Fig. 1). It has also been reported that Cu/CuCl electrode is affected by light in solution. The potential tends to more negative value when it is exposed to light⁷. Moreover photo solvation and photo decomposition of solvated complex has been suggested.⁸

These photochemical reactions at the Cu/CuCl electrode surface may be responsible for increased corrosion in presence of white light. Due to the anomalous photovoltages and micro semiconductor film junction photo diffusion processes are also going on⁹. Photo diffusion of Cu⁺ ions between the inner metal surface and the porous CuCl film in presence of white light is also one of the causes for increased corrosion in presence of sunlight.

Conclusion

In conclusion the investigation has shown that corrosion of α -brass in aqueous solutions of hydrochloric acid as well as of sodium chloride increases in presence of light which is due to the semiconducting photosensitive film of CuCl formed on the plate surface as a product of corrosion. Photocorrosion of brass in aqueous hydrochloric acid and sodium chloride solutions is proportional to the concentration of the solution.

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Direct Titrimetric Microdetermination of Mercury (II). Simultaneous Determination of Mercury (II) and Lead

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THE literature is not rich in methods for the direct determination of mercury (II) or the simultaneous determination of its mixture with lead. However, mercury (II) has been determined volumetrically with

KCNs using diphenyl carbazone⁽¹⁾, with CDTA⁽¹⁾, by titrating with EDTA⁽⁷⁾, with TBA⁽⁸⁾, and by reduction and then oxidizing mercury (II)⁽¹⁰⁾; colorimetrically using titan yellow⁽²⁾; fluorometrically using Rhodamine-s⁽³⁾; by chelation⁽⁸⁾; by reacting with 3-hydroxochromone⁽⁵⁾; and by electrometric titrations⁽⁶⁾. The present work deals with the determination of mercury (II) in microamounts by directly titrating its ions in the hippuric acid, using bromocresol green as indicator. Potentiometric titrations and results of analysis show that the complex between mercury (II) and hippuric acid is formed in the ratio of 1:2. Probably the following reaction takes place:

Similar is the case with Lead (II)

Experimental

Reagents: Hippuric acid (E. Merk grade), mercuric chloride and lead nitrate (Analar B. D. H. grade), Xylenol orange and bromocresol green (B. D. H. grade) were used without further purification.

Apparatus used: 1/100 graded micro pipette and micro burette were employed. Standard mercuric chloride and silver nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the exactly weighed amount in distilled water. Xylenol orange and bromocresol green solutions were prepared by dissolving 0.1g with 100 ml distilled water. Standard hippuric acid solution was prepared by dissolving the exactly weighed amount in hot distilled water.

A. Procedure for mercury (II): Pipetted a known volume of a standard mercury (II) solution into a beaker, diluted with distilled water to 30 ml and added 2-3 drops of bromocresol green. Titrated the green coloured solution with standard hippuric acid solution to the first sharp colour change to the oil of winter green.

B. Procedure for the simultaneous determination of Lead and Mercury(II): Pipetted known volumes of lead and mercury (II) solutions into the titration beaker and diluted to 30 ml by adding distilled water. Added 2-3 drops of Xylenol orange. Titrated the pink coloured solution with standard hippuric acid solution to the first sharp colour change to pale yellow. To the same solution added bromocresol green and determined mercury (II) following (A).

Results and Discussion

Results are given in Table 1 and 2. Lead and Mercury (II) determinations covered the ranges from 0.4127 to 1.0320 mg and from 0.3996 to 0.9990 mg with maximum errors 0.6% and 0.5% respectively.

TABLE 1. MICRO DETERMINATION OF MERCURY (II).

Mercuric chloride (ml)	Hippuric acid (ml)	Mercury (mg)		error %
		taken	found	
0.01M	0.0249M			
0.2	0.16	0.4012	0.3996	0.4
0.3	0.24	0.6017	0.5990	0.5
0.4	0.32	0.8024	0.7990	0.4
0.5	0.40	1.0030	0.9990	0.4